
PARENTING STYLES AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the “Parenting Styles and their Impact on the Behaviour of Secondary School Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria”. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study was twelve thousand seven hundred and thirty-nine (12,739) SS2 students. Six hundred and sixty one (661) respondents were sampled to represent the entire population. Based on Research Advisor, six hundred and sixty one (661) of questionnaires were retrieved. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23 was used to analyze the data collected to find out the frequencies, percentages and mean scores. The study employed both Descriptive and Inferential Statistics. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviation. At the 0.05 level of significance, the t-test for independent samples was used to test the null hypotheses. Where the calculated p-value was less than the specified level of significance (0.05), thus indicating that there was a significant difference, the null hypothesis was rejected. In contrast, where the calculated p-value was equal to or greater than the specified level of significance (0.05), indicating that there was no significant difference, the null hypothesis was retained or accepted. The study found that authoritarian parenting style had positive impact on the behaviour of children and wards and indulgent parenting style had negative impact on the behaviour of children and wards. The study therefore recommended that The Ministry of Education should organize guidance and counseling programs in the communities to sensitize and educate authoritarian parents to become more flexible with their children. Also that the Ministry of Education should organize guidance and counseling programs in the communities to sensitize and educate indulgent parenting to become more engaged in the lives of their children, indulgent parenting should be setting more rules for their children.

Keywords: Parenting styles, authoritarian parents and indulgent parenting.

1.1 Introduction

Parenting styles is defined as the patterns of parental behaviours and attitudes towards their children are recognized as critical factors in shaping adolescents' behaviour, psychological well-being, and academic achievement. Contemporary research in developmental psychology and education underscores the profound influence of these styles on various aspects of child development and adjustment. The primary parenting styles identified in literature authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful provide a framework for understanding these dynamics.

The authoritarian parenting style is characterized by high levels of control and discipline with low warmth. Authoritarian parents enforce strict rules and punishments, prioritize obedience and conformity, and often lack open communication and responsiveness to their children's needs. Recent findings indicate that adolescents raised in authoritarian households are more prone to internalizing and externalizing behaviour problems, higher levels of anxiety and depression, and lower academic motivation and achievement (Kawabata et al., 2021; Pinquart, 2020).

Authoritarian parenting has been associated with higher incidences of mental health issues and lower self-esteem in adolescents. The rigid structure and lack of emotional support can hinder the development of critical thinking and independence (Grolnick&Pomerantz, 2021). Educationally, these adolescents may exhibit disengagement and resistance to school authority, adversely affecting their academic performance and social relationships (Schrodt et al., 2022).

Indulgent parenting, also known as uninvolved or disengaged parenting, is characterized by low levels of both warmth and control. Indulgent parents show little interest or involvement in their children's lives, often failing to meet basic needs or provide adequate supervision and support. Adolescents raised in neglectful environments are at heightened risk for a range of negative outcomes, including poor academic performance, substance abuse, mental health problems, and delinquency (Pinquart, 2020; Schwartz et al., 2019).

Research on parenting styles in Nigeria highlights the need to consider cultural contexts when examining their effects. Studies have shown that while authoritative parenting is associated with positive outcomes across cultures, the specific expressions of warmth, responsiveness, and control can vary significantly (Akanbi et al., 2022; Akinwale, 2020). This variation necessitates a nuanced approach to understanding how parenting styles influence adolescents in Nigeria, particularly in the FCT, Abuja. Despite the importance of parenting styles in adolescent development, there is limited research examining their implications for curriculum implementation and educational outcomes in Nigeria. Existing studies primarily focus on psychological and behavioural outcomes, with less attention to their relevance for school-based interventions and educational practices (Okon et al., 2020). Therefore, empirical research is needed to examine how parenting styles intersect with curriculum implementation in senior secondary schools and to identify strategies for promoting positive adolescent development and learning outcomes. It is against this background that the study focuses on the influence of Parenting Styles on the behaviour of adolescents: implication for Curriculum Implementation among secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The problem of the study encompasses the practical challenges faced by school administrators, particularly school owners and teachers, in addressing issues related to

adolescent behaviour and morality within senior secondary school settings in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. One significant issue stems from the lack of parental obligations and involvement, which directly influences the effectiveness of school-based interventions and curriculum implementation. School owners and teachers of secondary schools often encounter a myriad of behavioural issues among adolescents, ranging from academic misconduct to social conflicts and moral dilemmas. These issues not only disrupt the learning environment but also raise concerns about the overall well-being and development of students. In many cases, these behavioural challenges are linked to the absence or inadequacy of parental guidance and support outside of the school context.

Additionally, the absence of a cohesive partnership between schools and parents further complicates efforts to address behavioural issues among adolescents. School administrators may struggle to engage parents in meaningful dialogue and collaboration, hindering the implementation of holistic interventions that address underlying factors contributing to problematic behaviours. Consequently, this study sought to find out the Parenting Styles and their Impact on the Behaviour of Secondary School Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to determine the Parenting Styles and their Impact on the Behaviour of Secondary School Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. establish the influence of authoritarian parenting style on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.
- ii. evaluate the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

This study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions:

- i. How does the authoritarian parenting style influence on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the opinions of respondents living with their biological parents and those living with guardians/foster parents on the influence of authoritarian parenting styles on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the opinions of boarding and day respondents on the influence of indulgent parenting styles on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is delimited to authoritarian and indulgent parenting styles and curriculum implementation. The study is also delimited to SS 2 students in senior secondary schools in FCT, Abuja. The reason for the choice of SS2 is because students at that level represent a

crucial developmental stage in adolescence where they are transitioning from childhood to adolescence.

Review of Related Literatures

2.1 Introduction

The following concepts are discussed in line with the subject matter:

2.2 Parenting Styles

The term parenting is not restricted to biological parents. Parenting is both a biological and social process (Learner, 2019). Parenting to Okpaka (2021) and Utti (2019), is the act of parenthood, child upbringing, rearing or child education. They further defined parenting as the family involvement process that consists of parents' attitudes, values and practices in raising youth. Parenting to Hilderbrand (2018) means providing care, support, and love in way that leads to a adolescents total development. It includes being responsible for the adolescents physical needs. It means creating a nurturing environment or attention, encouragement, and love for the adolescents. It also means providing guidance for the adolescents Hinderbrand (2018) further maintained that parenting also involves guidance, which refers to words and actions those adults influence children's behaviour.

Most parents establish certain guidelines and rules for children to follow. These help children understand what kind of behaviour their parents expect of them. Other guidelines and rules help children learn how to get along with others. Guidance is necessary to protect children from certain dangers. It helps children understand what type of behaviour is acceptable and what type is unacceptable. It also helps children learn the difference between right and wrong. Thus from the foregoing definitions, it could be deduced that parenting involves meeting the child's physical, mental, emotional, and social needs. Parenting is a complex process, involving much more than a mother or father providing food, safety and security to an infant or child. It includes members of the extended family, neighbors and every other person who in one way or the other is involved in the up bring of the child (Okpaka, 2021). It also involves bidirectional relationships between members of two (or more) generations (Forehand & Noussianen, 2017) noted further that parenting can extent through all of major parts of the respective life span of these groups; it may even engage all institutions within a culture (including educational, economic, political and social ones) and is embedded in the history of a people as that history occurs within natural and designed settings within which the group lives. Okpaka (2021) stated that the parents should be blamed and be made to take responsibility for the misfortune that befalls the adolescents. Based on that, Okorodudu (2018) maintained that the basis for good behaviour orientation and good adolescent's attitude development is founded on positive parenting.

There are different styles of parenting. They include authoritarian parenting style, authoritative parenting style, neglectful parenting style, and indulgent parenting style (Baumrid, 1991).

2.3 Parenting Styles and Child Development

Baumrind (1991) emphasizes that the way parents respond to their children's emotional needs shapes their attachment style (secure, avoidant, or ambivalent). In the study, these early attachment experiences are linked to parenting styles and how they affect the development of adolescents and young adults. The study suggests that the more autonomy, demand, and support parents provide, the more confident and persistent students will be in

their academic pursuits. This mirrors the idea in Attachment Theory that secure attachments, formed through sensitive and supportive caregiving, lead to greater confidence and exploration (in this case, in academic and social contexts).

Autonomy, Demand, and Support

The study aligns with the concept that parenting styles significantly influence children's long-term social, emotional, and academic outcomes. According to Baumrind (1991), parenting behaviors that encourage autonomy (allowing children to explore while offering emotional support) promote secure attachment, leading to well-adjusted children who are better equipped to handle academic and social challenges as they mature. On the other hand, parents who are overly demanding, rejecting, or inconsistent in their support may lead to insecure attachment styles, which can negatively affect students' emotional and academic success.

2.4 Parenting Styles and Secondary School Students' Outcomes:

The study directly connects the dimensions of parenting (support, autonomy, demand) to key outcomes for college students, emphasizing that parenting behaviors can influence not only academic performance but also psychosocial development and emotional regulation. This idea fits with Baumrind's position, which suggests that a child's ability to regulate emotions, form healthy relationships, and explore their environment is shaped by the type of attachment they develop in childhood, which is influenced by their caregivers' responsiveness.

Students with secure attachment (i.e., those raised with sensitive and consistent parenting) are likely to have better academic persistence, emotional regulation, and stronger social skills in college, because they have learned to trust their environment and their ability to handle challenges. In contrast, students with insecure attachment (due to inconsistent or neglectful parenting) may struggle with self-esteem, emotional regulation, and academic motivation, which could hinder their success in college.

2.5 Influence of Parenting Styles on Academic and Emotional Development

The study asserts that parenting styles are predictors of future performance in areas such as behavior, academic achievement, emotional functioning, and social skills. This is consistent with Baumrind's argument, which posits that the quality of the attachment formed during early childhood influences various areas of development, including academic competence and emotional well-being. For instance, a secure attachment fosters emotional security, which is vital for navigating academic challenges and social relationships in adolescence and young adulthood.

Similarly, the study highlights how parenting styles in adolescence affect not only academic achievement but also behavioral outcomes and psychosocial development. Baumrind's (1991) explain this by suggesting that children who form secure attachments are better equipped to handle stress and academic pressure, leading to higher success in these areas.

2.6 Authoritarian Parenting Style

Authoritarian Parenting Style is a restrictive, punitive style in which parents exhort the child to follow their direction and respect their work and effort. The authoritarian parent places firm limits and controls on the child and allow limit verbal exchange. For example, an authoritarian parent might say "You do it my way or else". Authoritarian parents also might spank the child frequently, enforce rules rigidly and not explain them, and show rage towards the child. Children of authoritarian parents are often unhappy, fearful, and anxious about

comparing themselves with others, they fail to initiate activity and have weak communication skills. Sons of authoritarian parents may behave aggressively (Schrettle 2020).

2.7 Indulgent Parenting Style

Indulgent Parenting Style according to Santrock (2022) is a style in which parents are highly involved with their children but place few demands or control on them. Such parents let their children do what they want. The result is that the children never learn to control their own behaviour and always expect to get their way. Some parents deliberately rear their children in this way because they believe the combination of warm involvement and few restraints will produce a creative, confident child. However, children whose parents are indulgent rarely learn respect for others and have difficulty in controlling their behaviour. They might be domineering, egocentric, non-compliant, and have difficulty in peer relations. These four classifications of Parenting Styles involve combinations of acceptance and responsiveness.

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the descriptive survey. This is because it is simply the best method for collecting information from a large population located at different places in natural setting and it is more accurate as in the case of study population. It is a design with attempt to document current collection or attitudes to describe what exists at the moment. Akeredola (2020) viewed the importance of survey research design with a common goal to collection of data from respondents. The data thus gathered from the survey shall be analyzed and interpreted. Survey research design was used to collect data using questionnaire items to document information which is friendly and easy to administer. The choice of survey research design was based on the fact that, the entire population was not covered, hence the use of stratified and proportional random design which enabled the researcher to describe and articulate information.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of all S.S.2 students in senior secondary schools within Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria, of which eighteen (18) are boarding schools and seventy (70) are day schools. The number stood at twelve thousand seven hundred and thirty-nine (12,739) SS2 students who served as the population of the study.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample for this study consisted of six hundred and sixty-one (661) SS2 students in Senior Secondary Schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. This sample was drawn from the entire population of SS2 students which stand at twelve thousand seven hundred and thirty-nine (12,739). The selection was in agreement with Research Advisors Sample Size Table (2013). The advisor helped to ensure that the sampling process followed a scientifically valid approach that aligned with the research objectives.

The researcher made use of questionnaire as instrument of data collection for this study was questionnaire titled (PSIBSSS). This questionnaire consisted of two sections. The rating of the response category shows: Strongly Agree (SA) 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and Strongly Disagree (DS) 1.

3.4 Method of Data Analysis

For data analysis, the researcher employed both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation with 2.50 as the benchmark mean. At the 0.05 level of significance, the t-test for independent samples was used to test the null hypotheses. All the null hypotheses were tested

at 0.05 levels of significance. Where the calculated p-value was less than the specified level of significance $<(0.05)$, it indicated that there was a significant difference and the null hypothesis was rejected. In contrast, where the calculated p-value was equal to or greater than the specified level of significance $>(0.05)$, there was no significant difference and the null hypothesis was retained or accepted.

4.1 Answers to Research Questions

This section presents the analysis of respondents' responses to answer the research questions numbered 1-4. Mean scores were used as the basis for decision making as stated in section 3.9. The analysis is presented below:

Research Question One: What is the influence of authoritarian parenting style on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 1: Assess the influence of authoritarian parenting style on the behaviour of students of Secondary Schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	My parents use capital punishment as a corrective measure on me.	168	164	174	155	2.52	1.11	Agree
2	My parents expect me to conform to their expectations at home.	177	191	161	132	2.62	1.08	Agree
3	My parents always make me carry out their decisions for my life.	116	114	209	222	2.19	1.08	Disagree
4	My parents punish me severely when I disobey them.	242	117	163	139	2.70	1.17	Agree
5	My parents easily get very upset if any of the children try to disagree with them.	112	172	221	156	2.36	1.02	Disagree
6	My parents have always felt that much force should be used in order to get their children to behave properly.	167	188	147	159	2.55	1.11	Agree
7	My parents do not allow me to question any of their decisions.	183	155	142	181	2.51	1.16	Agree
8	My parents exercise maximum authority over my choice and decisions.	193	169	146	153	2.61	1.13	Agree
Sectional Mean						2.51	1.12	Agree

The analysis in table 1 shows that the sectional mean of the students' responses on the influence of authoritarian parenting style on behaviour of students of Secondary Schools is 2.51 slightly higher than the benchmark mean of 2.50 and is interpreted to "agree" hence, it admits that the influence of authoritarian parenting style on the behaviour of students of Secondary Schools is positive.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of secondary school students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria?

Table 2: Assess the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of Secondary Schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	My parents prefer that I work without their supervision.	186	181	149	145	2.62	1.11	Agree
2	My parents do not direct my behaviour	117	159	187	198	2.30	1.08	Disagree
3	My parents do not challenge my activities and desires.	137	148	179	197	2.34	1.11	Disagree
4	My parents allow me to express my opinion on family matters.	215	189	131	126	2.75	1.11	Agree
5	My parents allow me to make decisions on most things for myself without their interference.	132	143	211	175	2.35	1.08	Disagree
6	My parents are not responsible for directing and guiding my behaviour.	146	155	168	192	2.39	1.12	Disagree
7	My parents hardly stop me taking major decisions.	151	183	162	165	2.48	1.10	Disagree
8	My parents believe that I am free to do what I want to do.	185	188	127	161	2.60	1.13	Agree
Sectional Mean						2.48	1.12	Disagree

The analysis in table 2 shows that the sectional mean of the students' responses on the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of Secondary Schools is 2.48 which is less than the benchmark mean of 2.50 and is interpreted to "disagree". Therefore, it holds that the influence of indulgent parenting style on behaviour of students of Secondary Schools is negative.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

In this section, the null hypotheses formulated to guide this study were tested using 0.05 level of significance as the decision rule. The t-Test statistics was used to test all the hypotheses for the analysis below:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the opinions of respondents living with their biological parents and those living with guardians/foster parents on the influence of authoritarian parenting styles and behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

Table 3: Two-tailed t-Test Result in Respect of the Opinions of Respondents Living with Their Biological Parents and Those Living with Guardians/Foster Parents on The Influence of Authoritarian Parenting Styles and behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

Authoritarian	N	\bar{X}	S.D	d.f	t-value	Std. Error	Sig.@0.05	Decision
Biological Parents	503	2.51	1.13	659	0.433	0.103	0.665	Not Significant
Foster Parents	158	2.47	1.13					

Result on Table 3 showed that there was significant no difference in the opinions of respondents living with their biological parents and those living with guardians/foster parents on the influence of authoritarian parenting styles and behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja ($p= 0.665$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the third hypothesis was accepted. In other words, the opinions of respondents living with biological and foster parents on the influence of laissez-faire parenting styles on the behaviour of students of secondary school are not extremely different in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the opinions of boarding and day respondents on the influence of indulgent parenting styles and behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Table 4: Two-tailed t-Test Result in Respect of the Opinions of Boarding and Day Respondents on The Influence of Indulgent Parenting Styles and behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja

Indulgent	N	\bar{X}	S.D	d.f	t-value	Std. Error	Sig.@0.05	Decision
Boarding	388	2.51	1.11	659	0.956	0.088	0.340	Not Significant
Day	273	2.43	1.13					

Result on Table 4 showed that there was significant no difference in the opinions of boarding and day respondents on the influence of indulgent parenting styles on the behaviour of students of secondary school in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja ($p= 0.340$, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance). As a result, the fourth hypothesis was accepted. In

other words, the opinions of boarding and day respondents on the influence of indulgent parenting styles on the behaviour of students of secondary school are not extremely different in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

4.3 Summary of the Findings

The following findings were made from the analysis presented in section 4.2 above:

1. Authoritarian parenting style has positive influence on the behaviour of their children and wards.
2. Indulgent parenting style negative influence on the behaviour of their children and wards,

5.1 Recommendations

From the study findings, it is recommended that

- i. The Ministry of Education should organize guidance and counseling programs in the communities to sensitize and educate authoritarian parents to become more flexible with their children.
- ii. The Ministry of Education should organize guidance and counseling programs in the communities to sensitize and educate indulgent parenting to become more engaged in the lives of their children, indulgent parenting should be setting more rules for their children.

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